

TABLE I

Dyes	Yield (%)	M.P. °C	Colour in Conc. H ₂ SO ₄	Shade on cotton	Pyridine λ max
A ₁	70.9	> 315	Deep violet	Chocolate	498
B ₁	79.0	309	Brown	Orange	491
A ₂	62.7	> 315	Deep violet	Reddish violet	501
B ₂	78.4	> 320	Violet brown	Pink	494
A ₃	65.6	312	Deep violet	Reddish violet	500
B ₃	79.6	> 315	Reddish brown	Reddish brown	493
A ₄	67.5	305	Deep violet	Pink	499
B ₄	80.2	> 315	Brownish red	Orange red	492
A ₅	73.1	> 310	Dark violet	Dark pink	505
B ₅	75.1	302	Violet brown	Pink	500
A ₆	73.1	295	Dark violet	Reddish brown	508
B ₆	72.0	> 315	Violet brown	Reddish brown	504
A ₇	73.5	> 315	Dark violet	Pinkish violet	510
B ₇	57.1	> 315	Reddish violet	Pink	506

2:3-Dichloro-1-phenylthioglycollic acid: This compound was prepared similarly as described above, yield: 13 g; recrystallised from hot water (norite), m.p. 130.5°. (Found: C, 40.64; H, 2.65%. Calcd. for C₈H₆O₂Cl₂S, C, 40.5; H, 2.53%).

6:7-Dichlorothioindoxyl: A mixture of pure 2,3-dichloro-1-phenylthioglycollic acid (10 g) dissolved in chlorobenzene (60 ml) was heated at 70° with phosphorus trichloride (6 ml) and stirred continuously for 1½ hours. Powdered anhydrous aluminium chloride (20 g) was added to the cold product. The temperature was maintained at 65° for 3 hrs. with constant stirring. The cold mixture was added to ice (100 g) and the chlorobenzene removed in steam. On distillation with superheated steam, 6:7-dichlorothioindoxyl (1.67 g) was obtained which was crystallised from petroleum ether, b.p. 60°–80°, m.p. 169°. (Found: C, 43.76; H, 1.88%. Calcd. for C₈H₄OCl₂S, C, 43.83; H, 1.82%).

Preparation of dyes: The general method for the preparation of these dyes has been the condensation of the reactants in equimolecular proportion in boiling glacial acetic acid in presence of a small amount of concentrated hydrochloric acid for 10 mins. The dye was filtered, washed with boiling water and recrystallised from suitable solvents. Satisfactory analyses were obtained for all the compounds.

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Structural Study of the Anthraquinone Glycoside from the Flowers of *Morinda citrifolia*

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IN an earlier communication¹ isolation of two flavone-glycosides and an anthraquinone glycoside from the flowers of *Morinda citrifolia* along with the structural studies of the flavone glycosides had been reported.

The present communication deals with the structural studies of the anthraquinone glycoside.

The anthraquinone glycoside, C₂₉H₂₄O₁₄, m.p. 230°, when hydrolysed with ethanolic hydrochloric acid, gave an orange coloured aglycone C₁₇H₁₄O₆ (m.p. 210°) along with D(+)-glucose and L(-)-rhamnose (paper chromatography and TLC). The colour reactions and spectral properties of the aglycone were like those of an anthraquinone. The anthraquinone skeleton was further supported by isolation of 2-methyl anthracene from its zinc dust distillation product. The compound formed a monoacetate showing the presence of one hydroxyl group. It was found to have two methoxyl groups² (Zeisel; I.R. at 2890 cm⁻¹). The ethanolic solution of the compound formed a complex with ethanolic copper sulphate showing the presence of a hydroxyl function in α -position to the >C=O function³. The presence of only α -hydroxyl group is also supported by the peaks at 1630 cm⁻¹ and 1678 cm⁻¹ in the infra-red spectrum and λ max at 410 nm in the UV spectrum

of the compound. The compound gave red colour on treatment with concentrated sulphuric acid, showing the presence of at least one methoxyl group in any α -position⁶. The product obtained after the sulphuric acid treatment was found to be Physcion (Amaz 290 and 436 nm, m.p. 207°). Thus of the two methoxyl groups present in the aglycone, one is at β -position and the other is at α -position.

The compound on oxidation gave 3 : 5 dimethoxy phthalic acid as one of the products which places the two methoxyl groups in position 6 and 8. Thus the aglycone is 1-hydroxy-6,8-dimethoxy-3-methyl anthraquinone.

The glycoside was non reducing and when subjected to periodate oxidation it consumed 3 moles of periodate per mole of the glycoside and one mole of formic acid was liberated. Thus the two sugars are linked as a bioside unit. Partial hydrolysis liberated glucose first showing that rhamnose was linked to the aglycone. The glycoside was not hydrolysed by taka-diastase but was completely hydrolysed by emulsion thereby showing the linkages to be β . The periodate oxidation also proved that the glucose and rhamnose are present as a 1 : 4 bioside. Since there is only one hydroxyl group in the aglycone at position-1, the sugar moiety must be linked at position-1. This has also been confirmed by UV spectral study^{4,5}.

Thus the glycoside is 6,8-dimethoxy 3-methyl anthraquinone-1,-O- β -rhamnosyl glucopyranoside.

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2'-Hydroxy-4-Methoxy-S⁺-Methylchalkone Oxime (HMMCO) as indicator for the Direct NTA Titration of Iron(III)

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THE substances reported in literature as indicators for the direct titration of ferric ions with nitrilotriacetic acid (NTA) are chromozurol-S⁺, pyrocatechol violet², N-benzoyl-N-phenyl-hydroxylamine³ and phenolic aldoximes⁴. The present article reports the use of 2'-hydroxy-4-methoxy-5'-methylchalkone oxime⁵⁻⁸ (HMMCO) as an indicator for the direct NTA titration of iron (III).

Experimental

Reagents: A stock solution of ferric nitrate (0.1M) was prepared in 0.1N hydrochloric acid and was standardized with Na₂EDTA using varianblue as an indicator at pH 2.4. A solution of NTA (0.025M) was prepared by dissolving required quantity of NTA in sodium bi-carbonate solution. 1.0% solution of 2'-hydroxy-4-methoxy-5'-methylchalkone oxime (HMMCO) was prepared in ethyl alcohol.

Titration procedure: Required amount of Fe(III) was taken in conical flask and it was diluted to desired volume. Then required number of drops of HMMCO solution were added to the solution and it was titrated against NTA solution from microburette. The equivalence point was detected by knowing the colour change from blue to yellow.

Results and Discussion

The effective pH range for titration of Fe(III) with NTA is 1.4 to 1.6. End point is also sharp. The results obtained show that in the determination of Fe(III) in small quantity, minimum amount of water to be added was 10 ml. However, large excess of water did not affect the results. The present method is applicable for the determination of Fe(III) in the concentration range of 4.0 to 16.0 mgs in 10.0 ml of water with $\pm 1.0\%$ error. It was observed that addition of four drops of 1% indicator solution gave satisfactory results.

The titrations of synthetic solutions were carried out at pH 1.6. At 2.8 mg concentration of iron 100 times excess of Na⁺, K⁺, NH₄⁺, Cl⁻, Br⁻, SO₄²⁻, 50 times excess of UO₂²⁺, 5 times excess of Cd²⁺, Zn²⁺, Al³⁺ and Mg²⁺ could be tolerated. Cu²⁺, Cr³⁺, Th⁴⁺ and anions forming stable complex with iron such as phosphates, vanadates, molybdates and tungstates interfered at all levels.

Ten titrations were performed with same amount of Fe(III) at pH 1.6 with four drops of indicator solution. The values of relative and standard deviations were found to be 0.80% and 0.36% respectively